

Template 2 - Surface analysis

Template to process and extract profile data from each incision exported with Template 1.

Quneitra, AOI 3, Incision 2

1. Load 2.5 point mesh of each surface/incision

2. Segment the surface and extract profiles

3. Profile metric analysis

3.1. Distance between profile edges

3.2. Area of the pit/valley

4. Advance contour analysis

